

**THE DIDACTIC METHOD – A LANGUAGE ELEMENT SPECIFIC TO
TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION
METODA DIDACTICĂ – UN ELEMENT DE LIMBAJ SPECIFIC EDUCAȚIEI
TEHNOLOGICE**

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Abstract: *The article presents the description of specific traditional didactic methods for the effectiveness of education in technological education lessons. Choosing a method that suits the students' learning style can increase the effectiveness of learning. Traditional didactic methods in technological education must be implemented in accordance with the specific learning objectives. Some methods may be more suitable for teaching theoretical concepts, while others may be more effective for developing practical skills. It is important that teachers take into account the specific needs and characteristics of students, adapt methods according to the context and be open to experimentation and innovation to improve the learning process.*

Keywords: *didactic methods, traditional methods, instruction, exhibition, technological education*

Rezumat: *Articolul prezintă descrierea metodelor didactice tradiționale specifice pentru eficiența învățământului în cadrul lecțiilor de educație tehnologică. Alegerea unei metode care se potrivește stilului de învățare al elevilor poate crește eficiența învățării. Metodele didactice tradiționale la educația tehnologică trebuie să fie relizate în concordanță cu obiectivele specifice de învățare. Unele metode pot fi mai potrivite pentru predarea conceptelor teoretice, în timp ce altele pot fi mai eficiente pentru dezvoltarea abilităților practice. Este important ca cadrele didactice să țină cont de nevoile și caracteristicile specifice ale elevilor, să adapteze metodele în funcție de context și să fie deschiși la experimentare și inovare pentru a îmbunătăți procesul de învățare.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *metode didactice, metode tradiționale, instructajul, expoziția, educația tehnologică*

The educational process cannot take place without applying *certain teaching-learning methods*. The teacher has the right to handle teaching methods in a personal way, taking into account his/her professional training, the objectives of the lesson and the type of lesson given. The effectiveness of the teaching methods applied depends on several factors, but it is certain that a well-selected and implemented method facilitates the learning process to the greatest extent, the method being an important means of increasing the effectiveness of teaching. The same information taught by different methods has a different degree of assimilation; for some the chosen method increases understanding of the information given, for others the acquisition of knowledge may be more difficult because of the method chosen. That is why the great teachers and scholars in the field have attached great importance to the methods chosen, studied the methods and analysed their effect on the educational process.

In the specialist literature the method is defined from several points of view.

S. Cristea [3] defines *the didactic method* as a totality of procedures and means integrated at the level of actions involved in achieving the pedagogical objectives of the training activity designed by the teacher. Also, this researcher reports on the method from two aspects: scientific and pedagogical. From the scientific point of view, the method is „a way of knowing” that generates information, principles, laws, strategies, educational paradigms. From the pedagogical aspect, the method becomes „a pathway”

for acquiring knowledge and skills designed to achieve educational objectives and to carry out teaching activity. The pedagogical quality of methods provides for their reorganisation from a path of knowledge proposed by the pedagogue into a path of learning actually carried out by the learner.

In another work, S. Cristea [3] states that the method is the most dynamic element of the educational activity, which, due to its complex relations between the objectives, content and evaluation of the educational process, presents itself as a resource of maximum creativity of the pedagogue. It establishes a two-way relationship of permanent interaction with the content of instruction and is confirmed or corrected by means of didactic evaluation.

H. Schaub and K. G. Zenke [11] refer to W. Klafki to define teaching methods. The scholar W. Klafki considers didactic methods to be all forms of topic- and competence-oriented teaching and learning, which are oriented to the diversity of learning conditions. Based on this definition, H. Schaub and K. Zenke conclude that methods have always served education in the process of processing the contents and objectives set.

I. Cerghit [1, 2] like S. Cristea views the method from two aspects: scientific and pedagogical. From the scientific point of view, the method is presented as scientific knowledge, activity based on knowledge, search, exploration, research of things or phenomena in order to find out the truths, obtain a result, in order to facilitate scientific knowledge.

From the pedagogical aspect, the method is processed as an instrument for transmitting knowledge/truths, it becomes a means of revealing truths, a way of forming in the minds of the disciples elementary representations of the surrounding world.

The scholar also points out that in a more modern version, the method is interpreted as a way for the teacher to help the students to independently find their own way in rediscovering the truths, finding solutions to the theoretical and practical problems they face in the educational process.

C. Cuciș [4] defines *the method* as the path leading to the achievement of educational objectives. Another researcher I. Nicola [7] argues that „the method includes a set of strategies through which it is possible to achieve new results that ensure the improvement and optimization of educational action. Being used by the subject of education, it becomes an instrument at its service, with the help of which it addresses reality in order to know it”. The method includes a set of recommendations, some general and others specific, which are intended to give a certain meaning to the scientific approach.

According to V. Pălărie [10], *the method* is a way to:

- Increasing knowledge, understanding, awareness of curricular content;
- Improving the capacity for knowledge;
- Regulating the stages of acquiring and applying knowledge and skills;
- Achieving goals, objectives;
- Generating a positive attitude towards one's own education, performance;
- Initiation of a more or less productive dominant cognitive style, bringing results, satisfaction, which constitute major formative contributions;

- Cooperation between the teacher and pupils, their participation in the search for effective solutions;
- The teacher's role as a competent carrier of the subject matter, as an organiser of teaching/learning procedures, as a facilitator, guide, evaluator, etc.

The traditional didactic method is an essential element of the educational process and has become the object of research in many scientific works in the field of pedagogy. For teachers, the method is a working tool that enables them to carry out the proposed tasks, and for pupils it becomes a pathway to knowledge, the road that must be travelled in order to discover the truth.

As an integrated part of the educational system, teaching methods have a specific status and involve the teacher carrying out specific tasks. Whereas initially the method was seen as a means of transmitting information for pupils to assimilate, today it is not so much a primary role. As educational aims, tasks and objectives change, so do the role and functions of methods in the teaching process. Teaching methods are modernising with the modernisation of education in general, as a response to social demands and the development of the modern world.

New, modern teaching methods are emerging, which tend to take the place of old methods. However, this does not mean that traditional methods are being definitively discarded, but that they are being supplemented by new ones.

Each method also has its own function, determined by the actions taken to achieve that method and the goals set. It gives the function a certain identity, personalization, thus the method of instruction contributes to informing the learner with the rules, the correct rules of action with a certain object or in a certain situation. There are also methods that achieve some functions tailored to set goals. Thus the discussion can be adapted to several specific tasks such as: obtaining new knowledge in the form of generalization of the information presented by the learners, fixing the information taught and checking the learners' understanding of it, checking knowledge and directing the learning process. This demonstrates that the methods are multifunctional [2].

Based on the formative and informative functions, a number of recommendations are made as to how teachers of different subjects can exploit the value of didactic strategies: selection and differentiation of both didactic methods and procedures in relation to the types of competences sought (psycho-pedagogical, social, managerial), respectively to the levels of complexity of the learning activities provided by the programme; encouraging the use of self-awareness and self-expression methods in order to improve pupils' learning performance; designing differentiated educational strategies according to the pupils' personality characteristics and learning needs; using a wide variety of resources to engage and motivate pupils in all aspects; the diversification of new communication and information technologies in teaching; continuous evaluation of the academic progress achieved by each pupil in relation to the pre-established educational goals [9]. To use the methods effectively, we also need to consider their characteristics.

G. Văideanu [Apud 8] identifies the following characteristics of teaching methods:

- It is selected by the teacher and implemented in educational teaching activities with the help of students and for their benefit;
- It presupposes communication between teacher and pupil;

- It is put into practice in the form of variants and/or procedures selected and structured according to the pupils' level of preparation, their aptitudes, aspirations and interests;
- It enables the teacher to use his or her teaching competence in the process of carrying out activities and transmitting content.

It should be noted that the lesson is a complex process in which several types of teaching methods are used. Thus, if we determine only one didactic method during the whole didactic activity, it will become boring and as a result the pupils' attention will be diverted in other directions of interest, which are not reflected in the proposed objectives of the lesson. In order to successfully carry out the lesson, the methods must interweave with each other, complement each other and be as innovative, creative and logically structured as possible.

Didactic methods have a multifunctional character and change their basic function depending on several factors such as the educational task, the proposed objectives, etc. The level of effectiveness of the use of traditional didactic methods depends to a large extent on the correct appreciation of their characteristics. The lesson is a complex process and requires the use of different traditional teaching methods, which fulfil different educational functions.

Traditional methods specific to technological education have their significance in that they constitute an experienced and well-known framework of teaching-learning strategies used in the technological education lesson. Traditional methods are understood to mean classical, dogmatic or didacticist methods, essentially those that rely on direct communication from the teacher [6]. These methods are simple, accessible and easy to organise and implement in lessons. They include:

Working with the textbook [5] is one of the most widespread and widely used methods in lessons, given that the textbook is the most accessible teaching-learning tool, a compulsory part of the instructional-educational process and an effective tool for guiding the themes of technological education lessons. At present, all schools in the Republic of Moldova are equipped with technology education textbooks that meet all educational requirements (accessibility, attractiveness, complex and varied content in accordance with the curriculum area, achievement of objectives, etc.). The textbook provides a selection, combination and dosage of the subject matter depending on the proposed themes and curricular objectives. It is the teacher's task to train students in cognitive and behavioural operations in accordance with the method proposed in the manual.

Working with images [5] is a method as well known as working with the textbook, since the latter is full of a multitude of images, tables, photographs and diagrams that complement the text and help to make the topics to be studied easier to understand. Its importance is underlined by the fact that technological education is a subject that needs to be covered not only on the grounds of theoretical information, but also practical ones, and the achievement of these tasks requires the use of certain samples, which is not always possible. In this respect, images are used, which present useful information that is easier to understand and memorise than written information. Thus, when teaching the cross-stitching topic, it is much easier for pupils to understand the steps involved in making the cross-stitch if they are illustrated with pictures than if the information is

described only in text form. Thus the informative and formative value of the images is irreplaceable. The teacher's role in this respect is to guide the analysis of the images, explaining where necessary. In describing an image, pupils are guided by their perceptions, sensations, imagination and reason. The most accessible method for this is observation. In order to achieve a decoding of the message conveyed by the image, a transition from spontaneous to organised, planned observation must be made. Thus, in order for the image to provide the pupil with as much information as possible, the teacher must guide the pupil in this respect by setting the following tasks: identifying the idea to which the image refers; working out how to organise the work on the image; setting the task of observation; establishing the stages of observation; assigning tasks, comparing, analysing and interpreting the elements of the image; evaluation of the result of the activity, formulation of conclusions.

The didactic method of working with images can and should be linked to other methods such as working with the textbook, observation, conversation, discussion, brainstorming, etc. This method is also linked to the pupils' experience, from their own knowledge of the given topic, from what they see in everyday life.

The discussion [5] is a method that encourages the active participation of children in discovering truths, formulating their main ideas on a given topic, internalising them and expressing freely what they have previously studied. Through this method, knowledge and skills are fixed and systematised, and a spirit of teamwork is stimulated. In order to successfully carry out this method, the following steps are necessary:

- Arranging the group of pupils (the most convenient ways are arranging in a circle or semicircle, so that the teacher and pupils can observe each other, feel equal partners in the discussion, and there is no feeling of inferiority);
- Formulating the rules for the discussion, involving all participants. Such rules can be:
 - Listen to the speaker;
 - Do not interrupt anyone else;
 - Raise your hand when you want to state your idea;
 - When you disagree with an idea, do not criticise the person who has put it forward, but give ample arguments in favour of the contrary view;
 - Don't make fun of others;
 - Participate actively.
- Presenting the topic of the discussion, encouraging the students to express their opinions, and active participation;
- Moderating the discussion. Formulating questions for a more lively discussion, encouraging students to respond;
- Formulating reflective questions such as: Why do you think so? What would you do in this case? Why do you think this was done? What would be a better solution?
- Allow time for students to reflect on the questions and formulate answers. However, it is not acceptable to leave too much time for reflection so that the discussion becomes boring;
- Offer support to more shy pupils, encourage participation by everyone;

- Emphasise the right part of the answer, but not the wrong part;
- At the end of the discussion the most important ideas are deduced;
- Thanks everyone for their participation.

We can also point out some general rules that must be respected by the teacher who applies this method, so he must be the one who guides the discussion in the necessary direction. The questions asked must not be closed-ended, contain the answer or imply a yes or no answer, pro or con; when the student gives a wrong answer, the teacher intervenes to correct the answer immediately, which can also be done through other students.

Storytelling [5, 6] is a method of presenting information orally. The teacher usually uses this method to present a lot of information in a short time. More facts, factual data are related and explanation takes a more secondary role. The success in applying this method depends largely on the teacher's vocation, diction and talent for engaging pupils with the information. Thus, storytelling can attract the attention of pupils or arouse boredom and disinterest.

Explanation [5, 8] involves the specification of new information, its clarification. It is used when learners do not possess the necessary knowledge for understanding and assimilating new information.

The method of instruction [5], favours the formation of the ability to appropriate and reproduce information. Instruction is used to demonstrate work procedures, so instruction means explaining and demonstrating correct work actions. It can be used at the beginning, middle and end of the lesson, and is subdivided into introductory instruction, current instruction and concluding instruction.

The introductory instruction is used at the beginning of the lesson, the teacher carries out the following activities: introduces the objectives, clarifying the content of the work task; names the way the workplace is organized; refresh the required knowledge; names and demonstrates the work actions to be performed; names and explains the most frequently encountered mistakes from previous practice; names and explains the safety and hygiene rules to be observed.

The current instruction is used when students perform the actual action. The teacher establishes the mistakes made by the pupils and clarifies their causes, demonstrates the procedure for correcting these mistakes so that the work task is carried out to the highest possible level.

The closing instruction is delivered at the end of the lesson. Here the main aim is to analyse the pupils' work, so the teacher demonstrates the objects made by the pupils, points out the mistakes made and explains their causes and how to prevent them, assesses the results of the pupils' work and announces the workload for the next lesson.

The exhibition [5] is applied at the end of a module or a series of lessons with a broad theme. Pupils are encouraged to look at the material on display in the exhibition, analyse it, research it and comment on it. The exhibition can be organised around different themes included in the module studied. It can be prepared by the teacher (e.g. at the beginning of a module), by the pupils (at the end of the module, assisted by the teachers) and in a combined way: by teachers and pupils.

In conclusion, a wide variety of teaching methods are used in the technology education lesson. Some traditional teaching methods are specific to the subject of technological education, such as instructing. Traditional didactic methods develop pupils' mental and intellectual processes, which encourage the acquisition of specialist concepts, knowledge of the subject matter and the formation of practical working skills.

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